

Impact of Transformational Leadership on Teachers' Job Performance in Delta State

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ABSTRACT

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The study assessed Impact of Transformational Leadership on Teachers' Job Performance in Secondary Schools in Delta State, Nigeria. It adopted the descriptive survey design and was guided with 3 research questions and 3 hypotheses. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 493 principals and 4280 teachers representing 30% of the population (14,762). A 52-item questionnaire was used for data collection. The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point scale: Very high Extent (VHE) – 4 points, High Extent (HE) – 3 points, Low Extent (LE) – 2 points, Very Low Extent (VLE) – 1 point. The face and content validity of the instrument was ascertained and to ensure internal consistency, 30 copies of the questionnaire were administered to one principal and 29 teachers at Government Comprehensive Secondary School, Tungbo, Bayelsa State which was not part of the area of study. The data collected were subjected to Cronbach Alpha which yielded the following reliability co-efficient results: 1. $r = 0.76$, 2. $r = 0.70$, 3. $r = 0.68$ with whole reliability $r = 0.98$. A total of 4773 copies of the questionnaire were administered and a total of 4476 were fully completed and returned, indicating 93.78% return rate. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviations. T- test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that transformational leadership qualities and impact are to a high extent in the schools and this has also impacted on teachers' job performance. It was recommended that school authorities should consistently encourage delegation of responsibilities and involvement of teachers and other subordinates in decision making to enable others contribute to the success of the organization.

KEYWORDS:

Transformational Leadership, Teachers, Job Performance, Secondary schools.

INTRODUCTION

Education is described as an instrument used for social, moral and economic change and development. It is considered as a medium for imparting knowledge, skills, values, and information. A country's progress can be seen in the quality of its educational system. Moreover, the COVID-19 epidemic, which occurred a few years ago, had impact on education around the world, (Hazzam & Wilkins, 2023; Muller et al., 2023). The practice of education is inextricably linked to the concept of educational administration, which bothers on leadership. Thus, management quality has a great impact on educational

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quality. Secondary school education is the second stage or level of educational operation in Nigeria. The national policy on education states that it is the education younger people get after primary education. It is the mid-level education between primary school and higher school. Akor et al. (2020) describe secondary education as a level of education that allows for further development of a learner for skills required to perform well in higher education or perform better in society. It confers certain features on the recipients that basic education does not do.

Leadership could be described as a process of leading a team with the same vision to achieve specified goals. Leadership styles are traits, actions, and behaviours used by leaders to influence the work of others. Leadership behaviour could be positive or negative. It is positive when it leads to the effectiveness of workers and negative when it leads to ineffectiveness of workers. Adopting positive

leadership behaviour can motivate staff to increase their ability to reach pre-determined goals (Indeed, 2023).

Transformational leadership has been found to have a positive impact on numerous important outcomes, of which performance is just one (Deng, et al., 2022). Transformational leaders are successful leaders in organizations because they strive towards attainment of organizational goals. Achieving the organization's goal is simply one aspect of management; another is inspiring members (Piwowar-Sulej & Iqbal, 2023). The contemporary phenomenon of transformational leadership, as noted by (Shafi et al. 2020) is typified by attributes such as vision. Empowerment, staff development, supportive leadership, setting a positive example, innovative thinking, risk-taking courage, inspiring others, winning their respect and loyalty, intellectual stimulation and consideration for others (Nguyen et al., 2023). In a school setting, leadership is a procedure by which a head of organization impacts, controls and facilitates the exercise of teachers to accomplish the desirable destinations and objectives. Improving organizational performance is extremely dependent on leaders' styles of leadership. An environment where employees feel free to communicate their ideas, opinions and proposal is fostered by inclusive leadership (Siyal et al., 2023) and transformational leadership can inspire and raise employees' passion for their work, which in turn improves organizational performance (Sarwar et al., 2023; Le & Le, 2021).

Generally speaking, teachers play an important role in the process because they are the country's first responders (Aheri et al., 2023). The teachers are the main performers particularly in the teaching and learning process. They are the dominant group in terms of knowledge transfer and character development. The teacher is the most crucial factor in academic achievement (Mardalena, et al., 2024). In organizations, employees' performance is the key indicator of the company's success. In the same vein, teachers are the factor that influences students' cognitive, emotional and psychomotor abilities. Performance is the main factor that determines whether or not an organization achieves its goals (Riyanto et al., 2021; Wijaya et al., 2021). Transformational leadership offered by principals is therefore essential for teachers' job performance in schools because an employees motivation inspires a great deal of enthusiasm for him to complete the tasks given him. This leadership style makes workers to be motivated to do more as they are usually part of the entire process of reaching decisions except in the area of the final nod on the decision.

Transformational leadership is therefore another world view of leadership. The heads of institutions are the individuals who inspire and move their subordinates as they are ready to get the work completed willingly with utmost pleasure. It is therefore necessary that for getting the desired outcome, an organization should adopt the most productive leadership style. Although several studies have been carried

out on school administration and teachers' job performance, it is still difficult for school heads to apply the most productive leadership style in secondary school. This study tries to fill a gap in this respect by drawing attention on teachers' job performance.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Teachers are supposed to show a high sense of commitment in the discharge of their duties because the success or failure of the school depends on their level of productivity. Hence it is expected of the teachers to be effective in the discharge of their duties at all times. Unfortunately, there are indications that teachers no longer live up to expectations in secondary school. Many teachers go to class without lesson notes. Others do not effectively organize and manage their classes during lesson presentations. Some of the teachers are also in the habit of skipping classes or spending less than allotted time for a subject in the classroom. They end up not covering their syllabus at the end of the school term. All these have resulted to poor academic performance of students. Efforts made by Government to tackle these problems include organizing in-service training for teachers and the employment of additional qualified teaching workforce but the issue of low productivity of teachers still persists.

It is against this background that the study is poised to find out whether the deployment of transformational leadership practices by school administrators has any significant relationship with teachers' level of productivity. Thus, this study will examine whether school administrators' transformational leadership practices in terms of teacher mentoring, provision of ICT resources and involvement of teachers in decision making have any significant relationship with teachers' productivity. The problem of the study therefore is, what is the impact of transformational leadership on teachers' job performance in administration of secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria?

EMPIRICAL STUDIES

In a study titled "Transformational Leadership for Schools: A review of Existing Literature" carried out by Sadia et al. (2022), it was revealed that transformational theory had been extensively utilized in school leadership in Qatar. Sarinah et al., (2024), in a study titled "Transformational leadership on Teacher Performance through mediating Role Motivation", also found out that principal's transformational leadership had a considerable positive direct effect on teachers' motivation and this had a considerable direct and beneficial effect on teachers' performance. Okeke et al., (2023) also carried out a study on "Influence of School Leadership Style on Teachers' Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. The findings of the study indicated that the principals exercised a high level of transformational leadership style and low level of instructional leadership

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style. Based on the findings, it was recommended among othersthat the Ministry of Education should organize leadership capacity – building programmes to empower principals on the best practices of instructional leadership style that will enhance teachers' job performance.

In a study titled "School Administrators' Transformational Leadership Practices for Enhancing Teachers' Productivity in Secondary Schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria carried out by Nnaji (2024), the results revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership practices in terms of teacher monitoring, provision of ICT facilities involvement of teachers in decision making and teachers productivity. Based on the results, it was recommended among others that school administrators should draw up mentorship programmes for teachers. Atif et al. (2022) carried out a study titled "Effect of Leadership Styles on Job Performance among Secondary School Teachers. It was also found out that there was a positive and significant effect of leadership styles on the job performance of secondary school teachers. In a study carried out by Imakpokpomwan & Erhabor (2022) titled Principals' Leadership Styles and Secondary School Teachers' Job Performance in Edo South Senatorial Zone, Edo State, Nigeria, it was revealed that teachers' involvement in co-curricular activities is not dictated by the leadership style being adopted by their principals and this is germane to the physical and emotional development of the human community.

In a study carried out by Udegbonam et al. (2020) titled "Principals' Leadership Styles and Business Studies Teachers' Productivity in Secondary Schools in Awka Education Zone, Anambra State, the findings revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between principals' transactional leadership style and productivity of business studies teachers in secondary schools. Okoroma & Agbo (2022) carried out a study on "Influence of Principals' Leadership Styles on Job Performance of Teachers in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Etche and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The findings revealed that democratic and transactional leadership style of principals to a high extent influence job performance of teachers. It was therefore recommended among others that seminars and workshops should be conducted by the Ministry of Education to stress the importance of democratic leadership style to principals.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to assess the impact of transformational leadership style on teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta State. Specifically the objectives are:

1. To determine the qualities of principals' transformational leadership style exhibited in administration of secondary schools.

2. To find out the impact of principal's transformational leadership style on teachers' job performance in secondary schools.
3. To determine the impact of Principals' instructional leadership strategies on teachers' job performance in secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the qualities of principals' transformational leadership style exhibited in administration of secondary schools?
2. What are the impacts of principal's transformational leadership style on teachers' job performance in secondary schools?
3. What are the impacts of Principals' instructional leadership strategies on teachers' job performance in secondary schools?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers transformational leadership style exhibited in administration of secondary schools.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on impact of transformational leadership style on teachers' job performance in administration of secondary schools.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on impact of instructional leadership strategies on teachers' job performance in administration of secondary schools.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted descriptive survey design. The study assessed Impact of Transformational Leadership Style on Teachers' Job Performance in Secondary Schools in Delta State. In this study, descriptive survey is suitable because there is no manipulation of data (Okoro 2024). The targeted population of this study is 14,762. The breakdown is 4280 teachers, and 493 principals in 493 Public Secondary schools in Delta State. The study adopted purposive sampling technique to select 30% of the 14,762 population for the study which gave a total of 4773 respondents: 493 principals and 4280 teachers. A 52-item questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two parts. Part A contained five (5) items of demographic variables of the respondents – Name of school, Rank, Sex, Job experience, School location. Part B contained 47 items based on the three(3) research questions in a cluster form: B1, What are the qualities of principals' transformational leadership style exhibited in administration of secondary schools contained

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16 items. B2, What are the impacts of principals' transformational leadership style on teachers' job performance? contained 21 items. B3. What are the impacts of principals' instructional leadership strategies on teachers' job performance? contained 10 items. The questionnaire is structured on a 4-point scale of responses: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), Very Low Extent (VLE).

There was face and content validity of the instrument. The questionnaire constructed was given to three experts in Education Administration and two experts in Measurement and Evaluation in Delta State University, Abraka. The experts made necessary corrections and suggestions which were effected before the final copy was written.

The reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach's Alpha statistics. The split-half reliability method was employed using 1 principal and 29 teachers from Government Comprehensive Secondary School, Tungbo, Bayelsa State, which is outside the scope of the study. The Spearman-Brown prophecy formula was used to obtain the reliability of the whole test (step-up). Section-by-section and overall reliability analyses were conducted on

the instrument to determine the reliability of each section and the entire instrument. The reliability coefficient of each of the sections is: Research Question 1 $r = 0.76$; Research Question 2 $r = 0.70$; Research Question 3 $r = 0.68$; and Whole reliability, $r = 0.98$. The reliability correlation coefficient values were higher than 0.60, which is reliable and appropriate for use in the study.

A total of 4773 copies of the questionnaire were administered. The breakdown is as follows: 493 principals and 4280 teachers in 493 Public secondary schools in Delta State. With the help of 2 research assistants in each school, a total of 4476 were fully completed and returned within a period of two weeks. There was return rate of 93.78%.

The data collected were weighted and analyzed as follows: Very High Extent (VHE) – 4 points, High Extent (HE)- 3 points, Low Extent (LE)- 2 points, Very Low Extent (VLE)-1 point. In decision rule, any item with a mean score of 2.5 and above is regarded as High Extent, while any item below 2.5 is regarded as Low Extent. T-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. If t-calculated value is less than t-critical, hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, if the t-calculated value is greater than t-critical, hypothesis is rejected.

RESULT

Research Question 1:

1. What are the qualities of principals' transformational leadership styles exhibited in the administration of secondary schools? N = 4476.

S/N	Items on Qualities of Principals' Transformational Leadership Style	\bar{x}	Std. Dev	Decision Rule
1	Openness to new thinking	3.44	0.59	High Extent
2	Talent for broadening minds	3.15	0.60	High Extent
3	Committed to active listening	3.28	0.63	High Extent
4	Tolerance for intelligent risk	3.07	0.69	High Extent
5	Willing to accept responsibilities	3.24	0.72	High Extent
6	Trust for others	3.12	0.73	High Extent
7	Involves others in taking decision	3.26	0.78	High Extent
8	Innovativeness	3.28	0.69	High Extent
9	Develop new ideas	3.24	0.69	High Extent
10	Respect others	3.21	0.72	High Extent
11	Empathy for other staff	3.26	0.75	High Extent
12	Optimistic in taking decision	3.28	0.68	High Extent
13	Set goals to achieve	3.11	0.83	High Extent
14	Provide feedback to other subordinates	3.15	0.80	High Extent
15	Promotes team work	3.35	0.70	High Extent
16	Motivates me to work	3.26	0.72	High Extent
	Aggregate Mean	3.23	0.41	
	Criterion Mean	2.50		

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The aggregate mean of 3.23 (Std. Dev. = 0.41), which exceeds the criterion mean of 2.50, indicates that the qualities of principals' transformational leadership styles exhibited in the administration of secondary schools are high. All listed items are considered qualities of principals'

transformational leadership styles, as their mean scores exceed the criterion mean of 2.50.

Research Question 2: What are the impacts of the Principals' Transformational Leadership Style on teachers' job performance in the Administration of Secondary Schools? N = 4476.

S/N	Items on Impacts of Principals' Transformational Leadership Style	\bar{x}	Std. Dev	Decision Rule
1	Openness to new thinking increases my job performance.	3.17	0.84	High Extent
2	Talent for broadening minds increases my job performance.	2.98	0.79	High Extent
3	Commitment to active listening increases my productivity.	3.12	0.85	High Extent
4	Tolerance for intelligent risk increases my output	3.01	0.76	High Extent
5	Willingness to accept responsibilities makes me work harder.	3.15	0.82	High Extent
6	Trust for others increases my output	3.02	0.84	High Extent
7	Involving others in taking decision increases my job performance	3.02	0.81	High Extent
8	Innovativeness helps me to increase my job performance	3.19	0.80	High Extent
9	Ability to develop new ideas increases my productivity	3.13	0.80	High Extent
10	Respect for others makes me to increase in productivity	3.09	0.82	High Extent
11	Empathy for other staff increases my job performance	3.10	0.76	High Extent
12	Optimistic quality in taking decision increases my job performance	3.23	0.79	High Extent
13	Set goals to achieve result increases my job performance	3.19	0.80	High Extent
14	Provide feedback to other subordinates increases my job performance	3.12	0.78	High Extent
15	Promotes team work enhances my job performance	3.22	0.80	High Extent
16	Motivates me to work enhances my job performance	3.16	0.80	High Extent
17	Permit group discussion on issues of school affairs which enhances teachers' job performance	3.19	0.88	High Extent
18	Accepts ideas from other teachers which enhances my job performance	3.06	0.90	High Extent
19	Empowers teachers in teaching which enhances my job performance	3.03	0.93	High Extent
20	Moral standing helps me to increase my job performance	3.23	0.82	High Extent
21	Discussion usually lingers for a longer time than necessary as everyone's opinion is sought	2.92	0.86	High Extent
Aggregate Mean		3.11	0.59	
Criterion Mean		2.50		

The aggregate mean of 3.11 (Std. Dev. = 0.59), which exceeds the criterion mean of 2.50, indicates that the impacts of the principals' transformational leadership style on teachers' job performance in the administration of secondary schools are significant. All listed items are

considered significant impacts, as their mean scores exceed the criterion mean of 2.50.

Research Question 3: What are the impacts of Principals' instructional leadership strategies on teachers' job performance in administration of secondary schools? N = 4476.

S/N	Items on Impact of Principals' Instructional Leadership Style	\bar{x}	Std. Dev	Decision Rule
1.	Helps in developing the school curriculum that increases my job performance	3.21	0.75	High Extent
2.	Guides us in managing instructional time which increases my job performance	3.20	0.58	High Extent
3.	Provides opportunities for staff professional development which increases my	3.26	0.75	High Extent

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productivity

4.	Supervises teachers' lesson notes which increases my output	3.17	0.71	High Extent
5.	Observes teachers' classroom management practices which makes me work harder	3.24	0.76	High Extent
6.	Coordinates the school curriculum which increases my output	3.15	0.62	High Extent
7.	Communicates effectively with the teaching staff which increases my job performance	3.26	0.75	High Extent
8.	Checks students' note book which increase my job performance	3.07	0.81	High Extent
9.	My principal models effective instructional strategies for teachers which increases my productivity	3.20	0.71	High Extent
10.	My principal provides instructional support to teachers which increases my job performance	3.25	0.71	High Extent
Aggregate Mean		3.19	0.48	
Criterion Mean		2.50		

The aggregate mean of 3.19 (Std. Dev. = 0.48), which exceeds the criterion mean of 2.50, indicates the impacts of principals' instructional leadership strategies on teachers' job performance in the administration of secondary schools are significant. All listed strategies are considered

significant impact, as their mean scores exceed the criterion mean of 2.50.

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals' and teachers' transformational leadership styles exhibited in administration of secondary schools.

Rank	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	P. Value	Decision
Principal	493	3.26	0.49	.235	4474	0.815	Accepted
Teacher	3983	3.23	0.40				

An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the mean ratings of principals' and teachers' transformational leadership styles exhibited in the administration of secondary schools. The calculated t-value of 0.235 with 4474 degrees of freedom and the resulting p-value of 0.815 were derived. Since the p-value (0.815) is greater than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis (Ho1) is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals' and

teachers transformational leadership style exhibited in the administration of secondary schools. Both groups perceive transformational leadership styles exhibited in the administration of secondary schools similarly.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on Impact of transformational leadership style on teachers' job performance in secondary schools.

Rank	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	P. Value	Decision
Principal	493	2.88	0.69	-1.560	4474	0.121	Accepted
Teacher	3983	3.14	0.57				

An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the mean ratings of principals' and teachers' transformational leadership styles on teachers' job performance in the administration of secondary schools. The calculated t-value of -1.560 with 4474 degrees of freedom and the resulting p-value of 0.121 were derived. Since the p-value (0.121) is much greater than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis (Ho2) is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of

principals' and teachers' transformational leadership styles on teachers' job performance in the administration of secondary schools.

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on impact of instructional leadership strategies on teachers' job performance in secondary schools.

Rank	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	P. Value	Decision
Principal	493	3.18	0.55	-.171	4474	0.864	Accepted
Teacher	3983	3.20	0.47				

An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the mean ratings of principals and teachers' transformational leadership strategies on teachers' job performance in the administration of secondary schools. The calculated t-value of -0.171 with 4474 degrees of freedom and the resulting p-value of 0.864 were derived. Since the p-value (0.864) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals' and teachers' transformational leadership strategies on teachers' job performance in the administration of secondary schools.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings on research question one reveals that transformational leadership qualities including openness to new ideas, tolerance for intelligent risk, willingness to accept responsibilities, among others, are to a high extent. The findings are consistent with the earlier studies of Sadia et al. (2022) and Okeke et al. (2023). The null hypothesis on research question one is accepted.

The findings on research question two indicate the impact of principals' transformational leadership style in schools is to a high extent on all the aspects, including involving others in decision taking ability to develop new ideas, provision of feedback to subordinates, among others. These findings are consistent with the studies of Sarinah, et al. (2024) and Nnaji (2024) who earlier stated the impact of transformational leadership style on teachers' job performance. The null hypothesis on research question two is accepted.

The findings on research question three show the impact of principals' instructional leadership strategies is to a high extent on teachers' job performance in areas such as school curriculum development, instructional time management, opportunities for staff professional development, among others. These findings are consistent with the study of Imakpokpomwan of Erhabor (2022) who earlier identified the impact of transformational leadership style on teachers' job performance. The null hypothesis on research question three is also accepted.

CONCLUSION

The success and failure of every organization depends on human and material resources, most especially the human resources which is a vital aspect of leadership. The ability to influence the decision of group members towards goal achievement is the responsibility of effective leadership. Transformational leadership has the ability to make suggestions to superiors, develop potentials to growth, take suggestions from subordinates. Transformational leadership also has capacity to develop the best in subordinates with flexibility and resilience and create in them willingness to

accept criticism admit mistakes maintain high moral values and understanding of strengths and weaknesses of others.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made for the study:

1. School authorities should adopt delegation of authorities which is an important aspect of transformational leadership since it has the ability to make the organization to grow.
2. School authorities should involve subordinates in decision making to enable others contribution to the success of the organization.
3. School authorities should accept suggestions from subordinates in order to make them have a sense of belonging in the day to day administration in the school system.
4. School authorities should have a strong sense of integrity which is one of the important aspects for successful transformational leadership.

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